

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Michelle R. Maziwisa and Jaap de Visser

Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape
with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in South Africa is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of

Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of the Western Cape: Michelle R. Maziwisa, Jaap de Visser

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Tobias Fischer/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in South Africa	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in South Africa: An Introduction.....	7
2.2. ‘A Re Yeng’ Bus Rapid Transit Project: City of Tshwane	15
2.3. The Accreditation of Municipalities to Administer Housing Programmes.....	18
2.4. eThekweni Metropolitan Municipality: Expanded Public Services during the Covid-19 Emergency. 24	
2.5. Procurement.....	29
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in South Africa: An Introduction	35
3.2. The Amalgamation of Municipalities in 2016	38
3.3. Metro Open Budget Survey.....	41
3.4. The Formalisation of Development Charges in South African Municipalities.....	45
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in South Africa: An Introduction.....	58
4.2. How Amalgamations Are Planned and Implemented	61
4.3. Local Boundary Changes and Public Participation	66
4.4. A District Coordinated Development Model	71
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in South Africa: An Introduction	76
5.2. Intergovernmental Cooperation in Fiscal and Financial Management: Bulk Resources for Municipal Services.....	82
5.3. Intergovernmental Relations through the Lenses of the Intergovernmental Division of Revenue ..	87
5.4. Intergovernmental Relations in Integrated Development Planning.....	92
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in South Africa: An Introduction.....	99
6.2. Participatory Budgeting.....	104
6.3. Municipal Budgeting and Planning during Covid-19.....	113
6.4. Transparency in Local Government Procurement during Covid-19.....	120

Local Financial Arrangements

3.2. The Amalgamation of Municipalities in 2016

Tinashe Carlton Chigwata, *Dullah Omar Institute, University of the Western Cape*

Relevance of the Practice

Rural municipalities throughout the world often face a different set of challenges than their urban counterparts. In South Africa, the government has adopted and implemented many interventions to improve the state of local government. In 2016, some of the municipalities were disestablished and/or amalgamated to address challenges related to financial viability and functionality. The 2016 amalgamation process is an interesting practice that is relevant for the LoGov-project in many ways. It has implications on all the report sections from structures, finance, responsibilities, intergovernmental relations and citizen participation. It is therefore likely to be useful for comparative purposes relating to the urban-rural interplay in the participating member countries in the LoGov-project.

Description of the Practice

The number of municipalities in South Africa has gradually decreased since the ushering in of the democratic era in 1994. There were 1262 racially segregated municipalities in 1994, which were reduced to 843 transitional municipalities by 1996. The 843 transitional municipalities were consolidated to 284 municipalities ahead of the 2000 local government elections. After the elections, the 284 wall-to-wall municipalities became the first democratic local government units in the history of South Africa. Of the 284, 16 were cross border municipalities designed to integrate linked communities and economies on different sides of a provincial boundary. The 1994 to 2000 establishment, disestablishment and amalgamation processes were primarily aimed at democratising municipalities by, among other ways, bringing to an end racial division as the basis for the establishment and functioning of municipalities.⁷⁵

The 284 municipalities were reduced to 283 ahead of the 2006 local government elections primarily to do away with the notion of cross border municipalities.⁷⁶ Provincial boundaries had to be amended to realise this objective. The 283 municipalities were further reduced to 278 ahead of the 2011 local government elections. A municipal boundary review process ahead of the 2016 local government elections culminated in the disestablishment and/or amalgamation of 21 municipalities resulting in the number of municipalities going down to the

⁷⁵ Municipal Demarcation Board (MDB), 'Twenty Years Later: The Municipal Demarcation Board Reflects on its Contributions, Experience and Lessons Learnt' (MDB 2019) 8-9.

⁷⁶ *ibid* 15.

current 257. The process of disestablishing and/or amalgamating municipalities in 2016 was initiated by the national Minister responsible for Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs in 2015.

A government review of the state of local government in 2014 had revealed that only 37 per cent of the municipalities were functional and viable.⁷⁷ The other 32 per cent were almost dysfunctional and required support to get the basics right whereas the remaining 31 per cent were dysfunctional and required significant work before they could get the basics right.⁷⁸ Some of the worst performing municipalities faced viability and functionality problems. The Minister, relying on his powers under Section 22(2) of the Municipal Demarcation Act, requested the Municipal Demarcation Board (MDB) to re-determine the boundaries of about 93 municipalities to address these and other problems.⁷⁹ This request attracted ‘much criticism, protest and litigation, with opposition parties arguing that it was gerrymandering (ANC using demarcation to influence the outcome of the 2016 local government elections) and that the board was dancing to the Minister’s tune’.⁸⁰ This is against the background that the proposed re-demarcation exercise was to take place outside the ordinary boundary redetermination cycle of the MDB.

After considering views from the public and other stakeholders, the MDB proceeded with 21 out of 34 requests/proposals from the Minister.⁸¹ The main reasons for pursuing the 21 requests was to define boundaries so as to improve financial viability.⁸² As has been the case over the years, the process of re-demarcating municipal boundaries involved a number of actors as required by the Constitution and the Municipal Demarcation Act 27 of 1998. The key actors included: the MDB, the relevant municipal councils, Member of the Executive Council responsible for local government in the relevant province, Minister responsible for COGTA, affected communities, organised local government, and traditional authorities, where applicable. While several actors were involved, it is the MDB that had/has the final authority pertaining to matters to do with the demarcation process. The process culminated in the disestablishment and/or amalgamation of the 27 municipalities in 2016.

Assessment of the Practice

One of the pertinent challenges that have confronted the South African local government system in the past two decades is that a significant number of municipalities are not financially

⁷⁷ Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (COGTA), ‘Local Government Back to Basics: Serving Our Communities Better’ (COGTA 2014) 6.

⁷⁸ *ibid* 6.

⁷⁹ MDB, ‘Twenty Years Later’, above, 34.

⁸⁰ *ibid*.

⁸¹ *ibid* 37.

⁸² *ibid* 38.

viable and not functional. Despite being empowered by various resource-raising powers, they are not in a position to raise revenue sufficient enough to meet the majority of their needs and obligations. As a result, service delivery in these municipalities, which are generally in rural areas, semi-rural areas and in poor towns, is mostly substandard or non-existent. Some of these municipalities are located in the former homelands, which were reserved for the black population under the apartheid era.

The (re)demarcation of municipal boundaries ahead of the 2016 local government elections was aimed at improving the financial viability of municipalities and ultimately, functionality. Yet, more than five years later most of the newly created or amalgamated municipalities remain financially unsound and dysfunctional. This can be attributed to the fact that these municipalities inherited poor tax bases. The amalgamation process brought together a large number of poor households, most of whom are unable to pay for the services provided, under the same municipal jurisdiction. The implication is that most of these municipalities have to provide services to a wider geographical area but to people who cannot pay for those services. The amalgamation process could also have impacted negatively on democratic participation in some municipalities given the expanded boundaries and largely dispersed communities, which may make democratic participation and accountability difficult to attain. The South African experience may suggest that the amalgamation of municipalities is not necessarily a panacea for addressing municipal viability and functionality concerns.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

National Treasury, 'Municipal Budget Circular for the 2019/20 MTREF' (MFMA Circular no 94, Municipal Finance Management Act No 56 of 2003, May 2019)

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (COGTA), 'Local Government Back to Basics: Serving Our Communities Better' (COGTA 2014)

Municipal Demarcation Board (MDB), 'Twenty Years Later: The Municipal Demarcation Board Reflects on its Contributions, Experience and Lessons Learnt' (Pretoria 2019)

Steytler N and De Visser J, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2009)

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

